

OBSERVATIONS ON THE CHANGES AND INNOVATIONS IN NEWS AND INFORMATION BROADCASTING OF THE MONGOLIAN NATIONAL RADIO

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Abstract

In this article, the author observes the current operational state of the “Khurd” agency, which is responsible for preparing news and information programs for the Mongolian National Radio (MNR). Founded in 1934, the Mongolian National Radio transitioned from state control to public status in 2005. At the time of its establishment, the radio broadcasted news by having announcers read directly from daily newspapers. However, starting in the 1960s, specialized departments for news preparation were established. In 1993, the “Khurd” news agency was founded under the Mongolian National Radio. In this article, the author examines the evolution of the department responsible for news and information broadcasting at the Mongolian National Radio, observes the themes and content of the news programs currently being broadcast, and draws conclusions.

Keywords: Radio broadcasting, news and information program, “Khurd” agency, writing genres

Introduction

Mongolia began national radio broadcasting in 1934. From that time on, news regarding events in politics, society, economy, arts and culture, sports, and many other sectors of society began to be broadcast regularly. Until the establishment of television in Mongolia in 1967, radio was the primary source of information for Mongolian citizens. Because radio operations are prompt and can disseminate information to millions of people simultaneously, it is the most suitable medium for broadcasting timely news. In the current era of developed television and digital media, citizens have many options for channels to receive information. Due to the high number of competitors, traditional media outlets, especially radio, have faced the need to change and innovate their methods of information dissemination. In this context, it is considered important to study the changes occurring in the news and information programming of the Mongolian National Radio. The purpose of this research article is to clarify the changes in the content and form of the Mongolian National Radio’s news and information programs over a long period of history and to determine its current status. To achieve this goal, the following objectives are set:

- Study the history of news broadcasting on the Mongolian National Radio.
- Determine the percentage of total airtime occupied by news and information programs on the Mongolian National Radio.
- Observe the themes and content of news and information programs broadcast on the Mongolian National Radio.

To date, no independent research work on the news and information programs of the Mongolian National Radio has been published in Mongolia. Journalism history researcher Dr. L. Norovsuren in the textbook "History of Mongolian Journalism," Dr. D. Batjargal in "Introduction to Radio Journalism," and Drs. G. Mendkhuu and D. Batjargal in the book "Radio from A to Z" have briefly mentioned radio news and information programs. Young scholars who have conducted research at the master's level in radio journalism at the National University of Mongolia and the Mongolian

National University of Education have conducted research on radio plays and artistic radio programs. However, no independent academic work on radio news and information programs has been produced.

Research Methodology

This research utilized a mixed-method approach of qualitative and quantitative research. Document analysis, observation, and content analysis were mainly used within the scope of the research.

First, document analysis was conducted based on relevant books, textbooks, research papers, and archival documents to study the historical development, structure, and organizational changes of the Mongolian National Radio’s news and information programs.

Second, to observe the current operations of the “Khurd” news agency of the Mongolian National Radio, news and information programs broadcast between January 5 and January 11, 2026, were sampled. A total of 294 news items were registered during this period, coded by subject, content, and genre, and quantitative and percentage calculations were performed.

Third, using the content analysis method, the news topics were classified and analyzed into categories such as politics, economy, society, arts and culture, education, health, sports, and ecology. Also, the writing genres of the news (news, reportage, review) were classified, and their frequency and percentage were determined.

Fourth, qualitative analysis was performed on the form, structure, repetition, live connections, and program characteristics of news broadcasting using the observation method to determine modern changes and innovations.

By combining these methods, a relatively objective determination of the changes in the content and form of the Mongolian National Radio's news and information programs, as well as their current state, was made possible.

Results

The national radio was established in Mongolia on September 1, 1934, and began broadcasting current news daily. However, at that time, the Mongolian National Radio had not yet established an independent news editorial office, so news published in the daily

newspaper "Unen" (Truth) was read by announcers. Starting in 1940, by the decision of the Propaganda and Agitation Department of the Central Committee of the MPRP (the party in power at the time), a radio activist lecturer group was established, and radio lectures on scientific theory, history, international situations, and the current goals of the country were read monthly. This is considered the earliest form of radio's political and social programming. Throughout its historical development, the internal structure and organization of the Mongolian National Radio have changed several times. Observing these changes reveals how much importance was placed on news and information programs. For example, by the resolution 86/220 of the Political Bureau of the Central Committee of the MPRP on October 29, 1953, the structure of the Radio Committee was changed to include the General Editorial Board of Political Programs, General Department of Artistic Programs, Department of Reporters, Program and Broadcasting Department, Technical Control and Sound Recording Department, Department of Foreign Relations, Economic Department, National Music Orchestra, and Announcers' Department. The General Editorial Board of Political Programs included propaganda, agriculture, and foreign broadcasting services. In other words, radio news was prepared by the General Editorial Board of Political Programs (L, 2019).

On April 12, 1961, by the resolution 163 of the Council of Ministers of the MPR, the radio structure was composed of an information department, broadcasting department, foreign information department, program department, reference section, international relations department, correspondence section, "Modern Mongolia" magazine, clerical office, technical department, and administration. The information department became responsible for preparing radio news. Since October 1964, a specialized political and information program called "Erin Tsag, Uil Yavdal" (Era, Events) was broadcast. In addition to government decisions and activities, this program broadcast detailed reportage and interviews about the work and construction taking place in the country.

The next step in significantly changing the radio's structure and organization was in 1985, when the General Editorial Board of Information was established independently. At that time, the radio's general editorial board of information had 10 reporters. Since 1993, the general editorial board of information changed its name to "Khurd" (Speed) news agency (Tugj, 2020). With the adoption of the Law on Public Radio and Television in 2005, a new page can be said to have been opened in the history of the Mongolian National Radio. With its public status, changes gradually began to occur in the radio's news and information programs. As of today, the "Khurd" agency has a vertical hierarchy: director, editor-in-chief, senior editor, commentator, editor, and reporter. A total of over 30 creators work at the agency. It also receives news and reports from rural reporters.

Researcher L. Norovsuren wrote in 2010 that the work of the "Khurd" agency accounts for 23% of the total airtime of the Mongolian National Radio (Ariunzaya L, 2018). As of the first quarter of 2026, the Mongolian National Radio broadcasts programs for 17

hours a day. Of this, the news and information programs prepared by the creators of the "Khurd" agency are broadcast for over 5 hours. In other words, news and information programs constitute 29.41% of the total airtime of the Mongolian National Radio. In addition to broadcasting news at the beginning of every hour from 06:05 to 22:00, the Mongolian National Radio prepares programs such as the economic review, social and political "8:11" review, legal information "Soyombo" program, "Sports Echo," investigative "Barimt" (Document), "Review of the Parliamentary Session," "Curious Microphone" program, and the "Hot Topic" live interview program on issues that have attracted public attention. As of 2026, the "Khurd" news agency of the Mongolian National Radio prepares and distributes the following news programs:

"Khurd" news program: The MNB news program broadcasts at the beginning of every hour from 06:10 to 22:00, Monday to Sunday. The duration of one broadcast is 5-10 minutes. Its purpose is to promptly report news and reports about events that have occurred in the country and abroad. The quality of the "Khurd" agency's news program is better compared to other radios, but it repeats the same news 2-3 times.

"Mongolian Week" review program: Broadcasts on MNR on Sunday mornings at 11:00 and evenings at 22:00. This program reviews important events that happened in Mongolia over the past week. The duration of the program is 20 minutes. The review program is prepared by the editors of the "Khurd" agency.

"World Week" review program: Broadcasts on MNR on Sundays at 16:00 and again in the evening at 21:00. This program reviews the events of the past week around the world. The program lasts 15 minutes.

"Soyombo" legal information program: A program intended to provide legal information according to letters received from listeners. It provides professional legal advice to anyone who lacks legal information or whose rights have been violated. This type of radio program is very rare. Therefore, it can be considered a timely program in the current era. The "Soyombo" legal information program broadcasts on Monday morning at 9:10, evening at 21:10 (repeat), Tuesday at 10:40 (repeat), and Friday morning at 9:10, evening at 21:25 (repeat). It can be considered that repeating one issue of the program many times can lead to annoying the listeners. For example, the 8:00 morning issue on Monday is repeated in the evening and the next day, a total of 3 times. The Friday issue is unique compared to others. The program continues in a format where the guest of that issue answers listeners' questions by connecting via phone. It can be said that this form of program is more accessible and beneficial to listeners.

"8:11" political information commentator program: Promptly reaches listeners with information about domestic politics, government, and the economy on Monday, Tuesday, Thursday, and Friday mornings at 8:00 and 11:00 (repeat). In terms of this program, although it can deliver laws passed by the government and the current state of the economy to listeners in a timely, correct, and organized manner, the frequent repetition time is a disadvantage. The program lasts between 10-15 minutes.

"Tusgal" (Reflection) live information program: "Khurd" agency journalists say it is a wide-ranging program that can be compared to the "Tsagiin Khurd" (Time's Speed) news program of the MNB television. The program does not broadcast news, but broadcasts reports prepared on current issues and conducts interviews by inviting guests on topics of social concern. It can be called one of the major news programs of the MNR, lasting over 30 minutes in total. In terms of timing, it broadcasts on the first channel of the MNR on evenings at 18:00 and 22:00 (repeat) on Mondays through Thursdays.

"Barimt" (Document) investigative program: It is unique as the only investigative program of the MNR that uncovers illegal activities and informs the

public. This program won the "Baldorj" award for the best work in 2012. It broadcasts on Wednesday mornings at 08:00 and 11:00.

Hot Topic: This live program, similar to the "Tusgal" program, also consists of reports and interviews with guests on pressing issues. The program lasts 30 minutes. It differs from the above programs in its time schedule; it reaches listeners on Fridays at 14:10 and 22:00 (repeat). It also differs from the "Tusgal" program in terms of the issues raised.

Between January 5 and January 11, 2026, the Mongolian National Radio broadcast a total of 294 news items. Categorizing these news items by topic shows the following picture:

Table 1.

Classification of news topics broadcast by Mongolian National Radio from January 5 to January 11, 2026.

No.	Type of Subject	Number	Percentage
1	Politics, Government	82	28
2	Economy	56	19
3	Crime	35	12
4	Ecology	31	10.5
5	Health	29	10
6	Sports	24	8
7	Arts and Culture	24	8
8	Education	13	4.5
9	Total	294	100

As seen from the table above, the majority of the news broadcast hourly by the Mongolian National Radio is occupied by information about the activities of the President, decisions made by the Government of Mongolia, and laws passed by the Parliament of Mongolia. Following this, the economic situation of Mongolia (inflation, statistical data) and official information about the crime situation released by the Media and Public Relations Department of the National Police Agency of Mongolia occupy space. It was observed during the study period that the Mongolian National

Radio places great importance on ecological issues and weather reports, reporting on them regularly. During the observation period, news about sports and arts and culture were reported equally, while information about the education sector was broadcast in the lowest number.

Classifying the writing genres of the 294 news items broadcast during the aforementioned observation period (January 5 to January 11, 2026) resulted in the following:

Table 2.

Classification of news writing genres broadcast by Mongolian National Radio from January 5 to January 11, 2026.

No.	Type of Information	Number	Percentage
1	News	186	63.27
2	Reportage	73	24.83
3	Review	35	11.90

As seen from the table above, news dominates the hourly news programs of the Mongolian National Radio, followed by reportage. It should be mentioned that in recent years, the Mongolian National Radio has been undergoing changes in not only the content but also the form of its news and information programs. For example, it has abandoned having the radio's hourly news read by announcers, and now a senior editor works in the studio to present the news. Also, during the news hour, reporters connect by phone from the location where the event is taking place to broadcast explanations and factual information live on air. In other words, the method by which the Mongolian National Radio broadcasts news has changed to a certain extent, allowing it to be broadcast "live" in the digital environment,

and event news is being presented and heard by integrating the broadcast with mobile phones and social media environments in a "right now" principle.

Conclusion

After observing the changes and innovations in the news and information programs prepared and broadcast by the "Khurd" agency of the MNR, the following conclusions are drawn:

The "Khurd" agency of the MNR is performing its stated purpose well by promptly broadcasting news about events and phenomena happening in the country and abroad at regular times. The "Khurd" agency has not limited its activities to just broadcasting news. It is preparing programs and shows that reflect multifaceted social issues, including politics, society, the economy, and law, as well as investigative and problem-raising

content, at a high professional level. Other commercial radio stations operating in Mongolia are unable to prepare programs of the quality that can compete with the Mongolian National Radio. The creators of the "Khurd" agency sensitively feel current trends, modern social demands, and how listeners receive information, and have been able to seek forms for hourly news broadcasting and implement radical innovations.

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